

ROMO: Direct from Producer to Consumer – Innovative network connecting local producers with consumers

Problem encountered and objective

Small food producers across Europe face limited market access due to strict retail requirements, high costs, and complex logistics. This challenge was experienced first-hand by the founders of ROMO, who were unable to sell their high-quality, ethically produced food through conventional channels. ROMO was created to address this gap by connecting local producers directly with consumers through a simple, transparent, and community-based model inspired by the Finnish REKO system. Its objective is to shorten food supply chains, strengthen trust, reduce waste, and ensure fair access to local food for both producers and consumers.

Main results / outcomes

Since launching in 2020, ROMO has grown into a significant community-based marketplace. It now connects over 160 local producers with consumers through weekly pre-orders and fixed pickup points, currently operating in Bucharest and Braşov and coordinated via local Facebook groups. To date, ROMO has facilitated over 13.9 million RON in sales (≈€2.8 million), fulfilled more than 200,000 orders across 799 pickup meetings, and built a community of over 50,000 members. These results demonstrate that low-cost digital coordination, combined with physical meetups, can deliver scale, trust, and economic impact while supporting ethical and regenerative agriculture.

Practical recommendations

ROMO's experience highlights several transferable lessons. For producers, pre-order systems provide stable and predictable income, reduced risk, and minimal food waste without the need for complex digital infrastructure. For consumers, the model ensures regular access to fresh, local, and traceable food through direct relationships with producers. For practitioners and policymakers, ROMO offers a highly replicable model based on social media coordination, transparent logistics, and strong community engagement. Future development should focus on expansion to new regions, partnerships with restaurants and public institutions, and targeted investment in education and logistics to strengthen sustainable rural–urban food ecosystems.

Further information

[ROMO Braşov: De la Producător direct la Consumator | Facebook](#)

https://youtu.be/PRv20joLhm8?si=OJeWKwNy40ZGok_1

About this abstract

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EU4Advice aims to lay the ground for effective capacity building of SFSC actors, by supporting advisors as catalysers of the knowledge flow from research to practice within an EU network of SFSC advisors, and by promoting the integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS.